

Shaping Bank Trajectories during Disruption: Examining the Role of the Three Levels of Corporate Culture in Ethiopian Banks

Endalish Woldemichael Taye

A GradXs Scholar enrolled in PhD Program of Livingstone International University of
Tourism Excellence & Business Management
Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, endalish@gmail.com

Received: Sep 27, 2025

Accepted: Oct 27, 2025

Published: Nov 11, 2025

Abstract

This study investigates the role of corporate culture in shaping the trajectories of Ethiopian banks that are facing disruption, coming from regulatory reforms, technological shifts, and economic challenges, like no other time in history. Anchored in Edgar Schein's three-level model: artifacts, espoused beliefs and values, and underlying assumptions, the study examines how culture influences their ability to navigate disruption.

Using research onion model that shaped the entire method and materials, the study thematically analyzes data from 13 sample Ethiopian banks selected across generational and ownership strata representation. Findings reveal that while banks may share similar visible features and declared values, it is their underlying cultural assumptions that distinguish how effectively they adapt and transform. Where alignment exists across the three levels, banks demonstrate greater agility, coherence, and strategic foresight. In contrast, outdated, misaligned or performative cultures, where innovation is professed but not practiced, banks are stuck in fragmented or superficial responses.

The study highlights that culture is not simply a luxury or auxiliary trait, but a dynamic force with direct implications for resilience and future-readiness. By making culture visible, aligned, and actionable, banks can respond more effectively to systemic shifts. This study, using Edgar Schein's theory which is not usual for Ethiopian context, offers a fresh contribution to both organizational culture theory and the practical discourse on banking transformation in emerging market.

Key Words: Culture, disruption, regulatory, technological, and economic

1. Introduction

It has been nearly three decades since the Ethiopian banking industry, which only had state-owned players, opened its doors to private banks. For most of these thirty years, the banks enjoyed stability, steady growth, higher margins of profits, and a lack of imperative for competitive distinctiveness. Nonetheless, this circumstance has changed in recent years and the industry has been facing disruption after disruption due to several factors, including regulatory changes, technological advancements, and economic challenges. The entry of telecom operators as financial service providers, the liberalization of the foreign exchange market, the introduction of the capital market and interbank market, the inevitable entry of foreign banks, and the active and consecutive monetary policy interventions coupled with the looming trajectory that calls for a significant shift towards digital banking while trying to remain resilient in an economy that is hampered by multiple socio-economic issues have created a complex and competitive environment for the domestic banks.

Such unprecedented time calls for unprecedented outlooks and measures, and corporate culture emerged as a critical factor that is not visible, to the eye, but a powerful tool that shapes what happens in an organization, which is unfortunately most often overlooked.

Corporate culture is the personality of an organization; and an organization's culture may be one of its strongest assets, as well as its biggest liability. It has been argued that organizations with rare and hard-to-imitate organizational cultures benefit from it as a competitive advantage (Barney, Jul. 1986). Thus, in this context, deriving from culture is powerful for Ethiopian banks to effectively respond to the unparalleled changes, which are unfolding in the country. Nonetheless, due to the insufficient understanding of Ethiopian banks regarding the abstract but pivotal ability that the corporate culture possesses in influencing their respective companies to adapt, remain resilient, and prevail in this dynamic context, it was the least deliberately studied or crafted and placed aspect. Thus, this study set out to investigate the role of the corporate culture, particularly Edgar Schein's three levels, in shaping the trajectory of the banks in such disruptive times.

1.1 Objective of the Study

The primary objective of this study is to analyze the impact of the three levels of corporate culture, i.e., artifacts, espoused values, and underlying assumptions on shaping the trajectory of Ethiopian Banks during regulatory, technological, and economic disruptions. The specific objectives are:

- To examine how the three levels of corporate culture manifest in Ethiopian banks;
- To examine the role each level of the corporate culture plays in shaping the banks' response to disruption;
- To identify the most influential cultural element that enables the banks to navigate regulatory, technological, or economic challenges effectively.

2. Materials & Methods

To bring logical flow and flexibility to this study, the research onion was used and the entire process from the research assumptions, philosophical stance, approach, strategy, method, time horizon, up to the last specific techniques for data analysis was connected accordingly (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2016).

The ultimate goal of this study was to provide preliminary findings that would enable a better understanding of the market dynamics in light of corporate culture, laying a foundation for further in-depth study. Hence, the study was grounded in interpretivist and social constructivist epistemological assumptions, which view knowledge as something context-bounded, constructed and interpreted as social phenomena (Creswell, 2013) (Crotty, 1988). And this aligns with the nature of the research problem and the entire built of the study, which rather than seeking objective and generalizable truths for such fluid concept, explored how the three-levels of corporate culture shaped the respective responses of the banks to the external disruptions using the emphasis and lens of subjective interpretation and meaning.

Pragmatism bringing flexibility in method selection rather than adherence to single philosophical orientation (Morgan, 2007), the study adopted pragmatist research philosophical stance since it is all about navigating disruptions in the banking sector by drawing meanings from both objective realities and subjective circumstances (Goldkuhl, 2012). Although the selected philosophical worldview is open to employ multiple methods, the study used inductive approach only since it was appropriate for exploring under researched areas and constructing themes from observed data rather than testing predefined hypothesis (Thomas, 2006). By focusing on the lived and documented expression of culture in banks, the inductive approach allowed the evolving of themes that reflects how the three-levels culture functions during disruptive periods like present. The different essences observed in these three-levels of culture

across the banks explored displayed the difference it brought in their respective ability of navigating the disruption.

The choice, which was influenced by the study's aim to explore conceptual dimensions of culture using an interpretive lens, resulted the employment of mono-method qualitative research relying exclusively on secondary data. For such inquiry qualitative study is more fitting (Denzin & Lincoln, 2018). The data collected from annual reports (2022 – 2024) of the sample banks, organizational structure, new developments gathered from their respective official websites and other news outlets, strategy documents (emphasis on vision, mission, and values), regulatory directives and policy documents were analyzed using desk research method. This entire qualitative approach fostered a more nuanced understanding of how cultural levels are manifested and how they influence strategic and operational responses.

Since the disruption the Ethiopian banking industry facing is now and here issue, a cross-sectional time horizon was used capturing the data marked by simultaneous regulatory, technological, and economic disruptions. This aligns with Robson's recommendation for cross-sectional designs when exploring contemporary issues with clear contextual relevance (Robson, 2011).

The data were then examined using the process of thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006), which is a method of identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns (themes) within qualitative data. Themes were organized into the three levels of Schein's cultural model—artifacts, espoused values, and underlying assumptions. Themes, paradoxes and inter-level convergences were systematically coded and analyzed with the aim to: understand in what ways cultural patterns drive banks' resilience and strategic agility.

Triangulating multiple data, and employing conceptual lenses informed by both organizational theory and cultural analysis, the study sought to get at not just what culture “does” look like in Ethiopian banks but how it does work in behavioral action amidst systemic change.

Finally, purposive sampling was used to strategically select banks that reflects the diversity and similarity within Ethiopian banking sector. The 32 licensed and commercially operational banks are categorized into four categories based on their respective market entry period and ownership structure. Two are state-owned, while the remaining are privately owned by shareholders: first-generation, second-generation, and third-generation banks according to their entry. Thus, a total of 13 banks were selected one from the state-owned category and four from each of the three generational strata ensuring a balanced representation across institutional types, maturity level, and strategic orientations.

Given the fact that 32 being a relatively small total population but still impractical to include all bank in this one study, employing purposive sampling was appropriate. This approach is especially relevant in such industry settings where shared regulatory frameworks, market dynamics, and institutional trajectories create meaningful comparability within the categories allowing selected samples to serve as proxies for the group or theoretical patterns (Patton, 2015) (Robinson, 2014).

3. Literature Review

3.1 Overview of the Three-Levels of Corporate Culture

3.1.1 Organizational Culture Defined

Many scholars agree that organizational culture is described as the shared values, principles, traditions, and ways of doing things that influence the way organizational members act. In most organizations, these shared values and practices have evolved over time and became critical in determining “the way we do things around here”, offering insights regarding routine behaviors and informal norms that influences the performance of an institution (Deal & Kennedy, 2000). According to (Robbins & Judge, 2013), the above definition of culture implies three things:

- First, culture is a **perception**. It's not something that can be physically touched or seen, but employees perceive it based on what they experience within the organization;
- Second, organizational culture is **descriptive**. It's concerned with how members perceive the culture and describe it, not with whether they like it;
- Finally, even though individuals may have different backgrounds or work at different organizational levels, they tend to describe the organization's culture in similar terms. That's the **shared aspect** of culture.

Meanwhile, Edgar Schein claims in an era where so many definitions regarding culture running around in academic and applied literatures, we have to begin with a bigger conceptual map to have clarity of understanding and territory regarding this issue (Schiein, 2010). Hence, although his focus is on corporate culture in his entire book, he now and then refers to the four categories of culture he rightfully believes to exist, i.e., macro-cultures (national, ethnic, religious, and global occupations), organizational cultures (private, public, state-owned and nongovernmental entities), subcultures (job specific groups) and microcultures (specialization focused). After having this overall map, he defined culture accordingly:

- Through how we are supposed to perceive, feel, and act in a given organization, culture is the vital element that brings stability and rigidity to maintain the equilibrium of the organization;
- Culture is not only the foundation of the order within an organization and the rules the stakeholders abide by, but it also provides the language and the subsequent meaning to the routine;
- Culture is not something static; rather it is constantly reenacted and created by the interactions of fellow stakeholders and their behaviors;
- Last but not least, Schein believes that culture is a powerful abstract that can operate outside of the awareness of the leaders or stakeholders. If we do not understand this force, then we will surely become its victim. On the contrary, if derived from it, then it can serve as a powerful weapon to serve our cause.

Other scholars have also enriched the understanding of organizational culture by giving emphasis to different dimensions. For instance: (Hofstede, 2010) put culture as “the collective programming of the mind that distinguishes the members of one organization from another” highlighting how national and societal norms and patterns shape organizational behavior.

Through their Competing Values Framework, (Cameron & Quinn, 2011) identified four dominant cultural prototypes —Clan, Adhocracy, Market, and Hierarchy—each linked to distinct values and leadership styles. Their model is widely used in organization culture assessment since it facilitates the alignment of corporate culture with strategy, particularly during transformation. (Kotter & Heskett, 1992), on the other hand, distinguish culture between adaptive and non-adaptive, arguing for organizational with a culture that embraces change and innovation tend to perform better in turbulent circumstances. These complementary perspectives along with Edgar Schein's three-level of corporate culture provide a broader lens to understand how culture operates across different levels and contexts—especially within Ethiopian banks navigating disruption and change.

3.1.2 Overview of Edgar Schein's Culture Model

Edgard Schein three-level corporate culture model, which was initially developed in the 1980s and refined in the subsequent works, is among the most prominent, influential, and enduring frameworks in organizational culture studies. Schein conceptualizes organization culture as layered construct like an onion to be peeled to discover the core, each level representing varying degree of texture, visibility, and depth (Schiein, 2010). His model is displayed in three interdependent and layered cultural levels: artifacts, espoused beliefs and values, and basic underlying assumption.

Artifacts are the surface level encounter, visible to the eye, and tangible to all remaining senses. It is displayed in office setup, clothing, language, rituals, lists of values, technology, physical structure, emotions, stories and the list could go on. It is the most visible and feelable part of the culture through structures, processes, and interactions. Although artifacts are easier to embed and monitor, they are difficult to decipher without understanding the deeper meaning of their cultural context; thus, they rarely provide insights why the elements exist or the reason behind the organizational behavior (Schien, 2010).

As the name suggests espoused beliefs and values is the ideals, goals, values, aspirations, ideologies and rationalizations of an organization. They are explicitly articulated as they serve as guide or moral compass to an organization. Although such vision, mission statements or publicly stated goals are intended to be beacons of the organization, they might not always align with the actual practice or lack congruence with the practices that brings the effective performance of the organization into reality.

Nonetheless, it should be noted that this layer provides bridge between what is visible to the naked eye (artifacts) and basic underlying assumptions; and a framework which later, not in all cases, translated to deeper embodiment of the required behavior and strategic alignment (Schien, 2010). It needs to be underlined that when values align with the deeper assumptions of an organization, they contribute to internal coherence; on the contrary misalignment may result cultural tensions or superficial value adoption (Schein, *Organizational Culture and Leadership* (3rd ed), 2004).

Basic underlying assumptions is the most critical and challenging point for leaders who aspires to change an organization's culture since it is implicit and deep-rooted assumptions that actually shape behaviors and the way things are communicated and undertaken in an organization. These deeply embedded behavior, perception, thoughts, and feelings are often unconscious and taken-for-granted. Since stakeholders of an organization usually derive meaning and stability from these, it makes them difficult to change and an effort to do so would be time-consuming and anxiety provoking. The effort calls for high-caliber wisdom and strategy (Schien, 2010).

The core of Schein's model goes far beyond mere classificatory aspect and base its premise—to truly understand a culture one must explore deeper than the most apparent manifestation. In order to do so, he recommends iterative and clinical approach in inquiring about culture, which is akin to a therapeutic process where the layers of culture are revealed through repeated engagement and reflection (Schein, *Process Consultation Revisited: Building the Helping Relationship*, 1999). It should be noted that culture, in this view, is dynamic, multi-layered, and deeply woven in the social fabric of an organization. Particularly in contexts of disruption, such as that of the Ethiopian banking industry, underlying assumptions can be factors that brings steadiness and proactive action to prevail or a source of resistance to needed transformation.

Other scholars in their own way reinterpreted and expanded what Schein started in his model. Dimitrov (Dimitrov, 2013) conceptualizes the model as a “hologram,” in which the three levels are not discrete and static but interpenetrated and continuously reconstructed through social interactions. This holographic view highlights the dynamic and interpretive nature of culture, especially during periods of uncertainty. Others, like Raz and Fadlon (Raz & Fadlon, 2006), have critiqued the challenges of empirically distinguishing between espoused values and tacit assumptions, proposing alternative frameworks for understanding cultural congruence and misalignment. Saiyadain (2006) and Schermerhorn (2011) also offer valuable adaptations that emphasize the practical implications of Schein's model for leadership and organizational change.

In summary, Schein's model offers a powerful lens through which to examine how culture operates within organizations, especially under pressure. Its layered approach allows for both surface-level observation and deep cultural diagnosis. In the context of Ethiopian banking—an

industry marked by regulatory shifts, technological change, and heightened competition—this model provides a relevant analytical framework to explore how deeply held cultural assumptions shape institutional trajectories during disruption.

3.2 Disruption in Ethiopian Banking

Modern banking in Ethiopia dates all the way back to 1905 during the imperial regime. The banking sector since then has always been the primary integral part of Ethiopia's financial sector. Besides its critical contribution for macroeconomic outcomes and objectives intended to enhance growth, the industry has always been the reflection of the different governments' political and socioeconomic ideology (Abate & Kaur, April 2023). According to Abate and Kaur, the origin and development of modern banking in Ethiopia has passed through three stages: imperial regime phase (1905 – 1974), socialist state phase (1974 – 1991), and liberalization phase (post-1991), which I agree. The phases are basically defined by their different ownership forms and socioeconomic contexts. Nonetheless, I differ from the authors in putting everything post-1991 in one category since the third liberalization phase could further be decomposed and recategorized as a disruption phase due to the unprecedented changes witnessed in the past couple of years since the liberalization began.

Liberalization of the banking industry began as soon as the EPRDF took power from the socialist regime and adopted a mixed-economy system. Between 1994 and 1999, this brought six first-generation private banks owned by indigenous shareholders to the market other than the then three state-owned banks (Berhane, 2019). Despite the raising of the minimum paid-up capital for entry from Birr 75 million to Birr 500 million, the second wave that occurred between 2004 and 2012 brought 10 additional private banks, which increased the total number of private banks to 16 (The Swing of Paid up Capital over the Years, 2021) while the state-owned banks reduced to two due to the takeover of Construction & Business Bank by Commercial Bank of Ethiopia. Again, the paid-up capital requirement was raised from Birr 500 million to Birr 5 billion, a significant jump announced in 2020 with a five-years grace period (Lelisa & Tadesse, July 2024). Despite the increment of the minimum capital requirement, 14 new banks entered the market between 2020 and 2023. This time around the entry brought a diversified crowd that included full-fledged interest free banks, mortgage-specialized bank, and veteran microfinances graduating to banks (National Bank of Ethiopia, 2025).

Overall, the banks have now reached 32, and despite the increased number and the changes in paid-up capital requirement, the banks have been enjoying stability, steady growth, and higher margins of profit until recently, which characterizes the first leg of the post-1991 changes. However, in the last couple of years, the Ethiopian banking industry has been facing disruption after disruption due to several factors, including regulatory changes, technological advancements, and economic challenges. The entry of telecom operators as financial service providers, the liberalization of the foreign exchange market, the introduction of the capital market and interbank market, the inevitable entry of foreign banks, and the active and consecutive monetary policy interventions coupled with the looming trajectory that calls for a significant shift towards digital banking and possible merger or acquisitions while trying to remain resilient in an economy that is hampered by multiple socio-economic issues have created a complex and competitive environment for the domestic banks and banking as we know it is about to change, which in my opinion is the fourth and disruptive phase of the Ethiopian banking industry.

Speaking of disruption, its dictionary definition refers to the process of disturbing or interrupting the normal flow of a process, system, or environment (Merriam-Webster, 2025). I have been familiar with this dictionary meaning, but I only actually grasped the intensity it could bring in shaping, reshaping, and dismantling legacy businesses when I first encountered with Robert Iger's memoir, *The Ride of a Lifetime*. In his storytelling book in today's highly-

competitive world, changing customer preferences, technological advancement, and geopolitical shifts, disruptive changes are definitely inevitable and clinging to the past successful business models is also definitely sabotaging oneself to failure (Iger, 2019).

With this perspective in mind, disruption emerged as a defining feature that shapes the trajectory and resilience of organization across industries, including the banking sector. Disruption is multi-dimensional process, not a one-time product or occurrence, where smaller companies or new entrants with higher flexibility and agility could successfully challenge and upset well established incumbent businesses (Christensen, Raynor, & McDonald, 2015). In disruption incumbents could be the victim of their own past success if they don't have the culture of adaptability and cease being clingy to the business model that no longer works.

It is also important to dismiss a common misperception that technology is either the sole source of disruption. It is true that technology is one of the prime sources of disruption; however, Godart and Pistilli in their article emphasized that disruption is multifaceted coming from different directions and challenges industries and usually end up ending the world as they know it. The scholars named four typologies of disruption: technology, business model, regulatory, and social movement (Godart & Pistilli, 2024). While disruption can emerge from various sources as highlighted by Godart and Pistilli (2024), the Ethiopian banking industry is basically experiencing its impact from the three primary factors: regulatory reforms, technological dynamism, and economic challenges. These factors are not only going to intensify the competition and put the banks under pressure to remain profitable, but will challenge their very existence and solvency.

3.2.1 Regulatory and Macro-Economic Policy Reforms

Successfully concluding the first Homegrown Economic Reform (HGER) spanning from 2019 to 2023, various macroeconomic, structural, and supply-side reforms continued to take place under the second HGER 2.0, which brought several changes in the banking sector and brought new players in the market. This move is not only expected to open up the market and make it more efficient and inclusive, but also intends to drive higher growth and reduce inflation over medium term (NBE, November 2024). To bring the required improvement in every front intervention in key variables such as: tight monetary policy, foreign exchange regime change, and further opening up of the market, were undertaken which is for better or worse disruptive to the banking industry. Some of the changes for instance are summarized accordingly:

- New banking business proclamation no. 1360/2025 signifies notable departure in key areas from its preceding (592/2008) it just repealed on March 2025. These critical departures of the new directive could be summarized into four major highlights: first, the opening of the market to foreign participants, from banks that desires to open subsidiary, a branch, rep office, or invest in existing domestic banks to giving foreign nationals the go ahead to be the employees of foreign or domestic banks (with limitations); second, enhanced emphasis on financial stability and resolution that focused on maintaining the stability of the financial system including introducing resolution framework for banks that are failing or likely to fail while giving more legal clarity for actions that leads to liquidation and introduction of tools that enables to manage and resolve distress and crisis, such as: bridge bank and asset management vehicle; third, the upward revision of the maximum share ownership per natural and judiciary person and putting different limiting ownership between the two; and last but not least, the proclamation tried to update the regulatory framework in a way that matches the evolving dynamics of the industry and international best practices (FDRE House of Representatives, 2025). This proclamation not only further intensifies the already intensified competition, but also a clear indication of the changing market dynamics as well as the surging pressure for consolidation.
- Foreign Exchange Directive No. FXD/01/2024 superseding all prior directives marked a complete departure from a highly centralized and restrictive foreign exchange regime to

market-based ecosystem, aiming to encourage foreign investment, foster flexibility, and efficiency while equally intending to significantly narrow the gap with the parallel market and squash its influence on the economy. The liberalization of the FX market, while NBE's daily weighted indicative rate serves as a reference exchange rate, brought market-oriented ecosystem that enables freely negotiated buying and selling of foreign currencies, while expanding the market to non-bank participants to become a major player in dealing currencies and introduced inter-bank foreign exchange market. In addition, the directive relaxed the facilitation of international payments using debit, credit, and prepaid cards as well as cross-border capital transfers (with explicit limitations), and requirements on foreign and retention accounts. Meanwhile, banks are no longer obliged to surrender to NBE from their respective FCY inflows (National Bank of Ethiopia, 2024). This directive clearly brought independent forex bureaus, bank-affiliated forex bureaus, and other domestic and international players to the table, which brings new dynamics to the competition.

- The National Bank has also issued two fundamental directives, Interbank Money Market No. MFAD/IBM/03/2024 and Open Market Operations and Standing Facilities No. 001/2024, which transitioned the economy from direct monetary controls to market-based system. Both directives are intended to enhance financial stability and deepen the financial market; thus, the interbank money market (IMM) is lending and borrowing platform among the banks for short-term liquidity management, while OMO serves as primary tool of NBE to manage system-wide liquidity and guide short-term interest rates. Unlike the landscape banks have operating for decades, IMM requires enhanced, dedicated, and active treasury management, increases competition as it comes with transparent trading system, and serves as a foundation benchmark rate for pricing of more complex financial products that will be introduced in the future. Meanwhile, with OMO, clear boundaries and predictable interest rate, new profitability means along with associated risk factors emerged, and expected to ensure enhanced financial stability. For banks, if they choose to prevail the changes these directives will continue to bring, setting up sophisticated treasury operations that not only manages the daily liquidity, but also interest rate risk is inevitable.
- The setting up of the capital market under proclamation no. 1248/2021, ECMA on article 3(1) and ESX on article 30 – 31, introduced fundamental shift in the financial sector landscape that was heavily dominated by banks, in which savings and credit were the primarily vehicles of resource collection and allocation. The capital market, which is still at its early stage, is bound to bring more diversification and complexity to the financial ecosystem. The market is presenting parallel funding channels for public owned companies including banks through debt and equity instruments, and reducing the sole reliance on lending while simultaneously encouraging investments.

These are few of the directives presented as a sample to demonstrate on how the banking sector is being shaped and reshaped. There are other multiple proclamations and directives that are either in the draft stage or had already become effective, such as the Special Economic Zone Proclamation (SEZs) No. 1322/2024 that are intending to encourage other sector by transitioning industry parks to broader multi-purpose SEZs via the introduction of many infrastructural and service benefits as well as tax-exemptions, which brought notable departure from the traditional context by creating a parallel regulatory and financial environment that likely encourages foreign financial service providers.

Alongside SEZs and the above four rather discussed with relative detail, a range of recent regulatory reforms and directive—including the National Id (proclamation No. 1284/2023), a paradigm shift in customer onboarding; corporate governance directive (SBB/91/2024), ensured that board rooms would never look the same as they used to; cyber security and digital banking directive, and others—are indeed creating systematic disruptions in the Ethiopian

banking industry. These disruptions are not just mere regulatory compliance shifts, rather transformative changes in how banks operate, compete, and create value.

3.2.2 Technological Advancements

During the past couple of years, the Ethiopian banking industry has been experiencing notable shift from traditional branch banking towards digital banking. The now notable move is basically powered by mobile and internet banking, digital wallet and increasing onboarding of merchants on contactless payment platforms. A key enabler of this digital move is the National Digital Payment Strategy (2021–2024), issued by the National Bank of Ethiopia. The strategy outlines a roadmap for creating a cash-lite economy through interoperable digital infrastructure, financial inclusion, and a conducive environment for innovation (National Bank of Ethiopia, 2021). This strategy is further highlighted and underpinned since it was once again set among the five strategic objectives of the NBE in its three years strategic plan document spanning from 2023–2026 (National Bank of Ethiopia, 2023). It should be noted that initiatives are aimed at increasing operational efficiency, reaching unbanked populations, and enhancing customer experience.

Among the major shifts that are being noted in this front is the rise of fintechs and the strategic partnerships they were able to charter with banks. The prominence of such partnerships is expected to continue blossoming since such partnerships allowed the banks to offer swift, personalized, and data-driven digital services focused on payments and lending, especially in credit scoring and digital lending for the underserved segments and beyond (UNDP, 2024). Furthermore, the recent introduction of café bank branches and Super App platform by banks are redefining how banking services are going to be delivered and taking it to the next level by giving emphasis to lifestyle integration, customer experience, and platform convivence (Accion, 2025).

While full integration is far from realization, the banking sector is witnessing growing interest and discussion on how to integrate Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) into its core business to fully automate customer service, combat cybersecurity threats through fraud detection, and data analytics in order to personalize services. Even though such discussions that are being made in behind closed doors are difficult to substantiate with hard evidence until they materialize, AI training program initiative for digital finance professionals launched by Mastercard Foundation and Kifiya Technology is a clear indicator of the interest and readiness of the sector to build capacity in this regard (Mastercard Foundation , 2025).

Moreover, Ethiopia liberalizing its telecom sector followed by the licensing of Ethio Telecom to provide financial services, such as mobile money and related financial products, and later Safaricom, the country's second mobile operator, securing the same license has been having a notable implication on the financial landscape which has been dominated by banks for far too long. Sitting on a wealth of data, the mobile network operators introduced Super App mobile money platforms—Telebirr and M-Pesa, which completely transformed transactional services and a direct competition for the traditional banks (PYMNTS, 2022).

Having to entertain these technological advancements coming from the competitors within that are chartering the new trend and external providers such as telecom operators and of course the direction the country is pursuing to realize digital transformation is disrupting the traditional banking model and putting the banks under pressure for considerable change. For banks, completely revamping their service and products and integrating advanced technologies with everything they do to remain relevant and competitive in the market is no longer an option but a strategic alignment requiring a deep cultural alignment to ensure successful adoption and organizational resilience.

3.2.3 Economic Challenges

The Ethiopian economy, although resilient, has been under stress for the past couple of years due to the overlapping factors coming from domestic and global challenges, and the banking sector meanwhile has been navigating this turbulent situation. Although the digital economy direction and financial market modernization and liberalization has been offering emerging opportunities, the broader macroeconomic, geopolitical tension, persisting conflicts in different parts of the country, and operational contexts has placed considerable pressure on banks, testing their resilience, adaptability, and strategic capability.

Ethiopia is just coming out of a staggering inflation, in which the headline inflation exceeded 30% persistently in 2022 and 2023, exhibiting decline to a little over 26 percent by the end of 2024 (National Bank of Ethiopia, 2025) following multiple and notable macro-economic reforms placed to bring the required balance in the economy and its real GDP is estimated to have grown by 8.4% during the 2024/25 FY (Ministry of Planning and Development, 2025). This macroeconomic strain was driven by domestic structural and social factors: such as, supply side constraints in agriculture and energy and conflicts in three regions of the country; and external shocks, which brought imported inflation especially since the start of Russia-Ukraine war that disrupted global commodity markets (FAO, 2023).

Domestically, the conflict and insecurity in Tigray region that lasted between 2020 and 2022, Amhara region since 2023, and Oromia regions not only brought humanitarian crisis, but also disrupted transportation corridors, damaged infrastructures, and displaced communities, which directly impaired banking operations and their continued service (Ministry of Finance, 2023). Internationally, the ongoing Russia-Ukraine war led to notable disruption across the globe particularly the price of grain, fertilizer, and energy soared sharply since the combined market share of Russia and Ukraine in wheat export is 29% of the global market and Europe's notable dependence on Russian natural gas and oil. Furthermore, the Israel-Hamas conflict brought close to home implications as it exacerbated oil price volatility and maritime insecurity in the Red Sea and Suez Canal corridor, which further disrupted the supply chain. For a country like Ethiopia, which is heavily reliant on imported fertilizer and gas, the sharply soaring price coupled with increased shipping costs, import delays, and insurance premiums, contributed to intensified inflationary pressures and business fragility (UNCTAD, 2022) (World Bank, 2025). This in return put the international banking operations and asset quality of the domestic banks under pressure.

Before improvements are being noted since the liberalization of foreign exchange market and some are still lingering, which fundamentally narrowed the gap between the formal and parallel market, fostered flexibility, and bring the high anticipation of long-term favorable implications on the economy, the chronic shortage of foreign currency, persistent trade deficit, limited export diversification, and growing external debt that put significant pressure on the foreign currency reserve have put the major economic constraints on Ethiopia. These forced the domestic banks to ration FX allocations, especially import related businesses and for international travelers, limiting support for international transaction and investment and ultimately undermining client satisfaction (World Bank, 2023) (National Bank of Ethiopia, 2023)

Collectively these conditions increased credit risk of multiple sectors that are import dependent, affected by supply chain volatility, and highly exposed to inflation, agribusiness, construction, and construction. Thus, the banks experienced rise of non-performing loans, declining margins, and operational disruptions (NBE, 2024). In general, the Ethiopian banking industry, despite the policy responsiveness, technological advancement, the yet to be fully tapped market, and the subsequent opportunities that is coming from these aspects, due to the cumulative weight of inflation, geopolitical risks, supply chain disruption, the domestic instability, the foreign currency scarcity, and growth deceleration finds itself in a particularly challenging economic moment. This in return created an operating environment that is structurally constrained and

volatile especially in locations stated above; and these circumstances not only requires technical capability, but also cultural resilience and strategi foresight.

3.3 Relevance of the Three Levels of Corporate Culture during Disruption

Before dwelling on the relevance of the three-levels, let's take a step back and quickly reflect on disruption and the interaction it has with overall corporate culture. Disruption basically challenges the very stability of organizations in all senses and requires them to re-look their internal capabilities and dynamics. In such occasions, culture ceases to be in the back sit and takes an active role in shaping the responses as well as the trajectory of the organization. And Schein's three-level corporate culture framework, i.e., artifacts, espoused beliefs and values, and underlying assumptions, provides powerful diagnostic approach for examining the very culture that fosters responses, which subsequently contributes in significantly sealing the fate of an organization. This layered model is instrumental, particularly in complex context like the Ethiopian banking industry where the regulatory reforms, technological shifts, and economic challenges converge, in identifying whether the banks are adapting and responding in a meaningful way or otherwise (Dimitrov, 2013) (Schien, 2010).

The most visible elements of the culture, artifacts, reflects how the banks are apparently responding to disruption. For instance, through new setups on the look and feel, technologies they are adopting, the constant languages they are now using, and the new or sustained routines. The shift towards digital migration, mobile-first platforms, strategic partnerships that spans from sectors that closely tied to those that traditionally doesn't seem to likely form allegiance with the banking industry, and redesigning of service centers that extends to a complete rebranding are among the attempts that are being made to cope up with the constant changes. Nonetheless, these shifts and transformations might end up being cosmetic in response to the disruption if they are not supported with deeper cultural layers, this is an issue in which Schein underlines about artifacts remain superficial if they are not embedded in congruent cultural beliefs (Schein, *Organizational Culture and Leadership* (3rd ed), 2004).

In a turbulent context, like the Ethiopian banks, publicly declared ethical commitments, visions, and aspirations plays significant role. Banks that explicitly articulated their respective aspirations, digital orientation, adaptability to the changes that are happening right now or will continue to do so, inclusivity, and others may perform better, provided these espoused beliefs and values align with actual practices. Yet, it should be noted that researches indicate that we should take caution against assuming stated values automatically equates to lived experiences; since misalignment between the two can lead to strategic discord and credibility that might tank eventually (Cameron & Quinn, 2011) (Kotter & Heskett, 1992).

At the core, of responses to disruption and the subsequent outcomes, are the underlying assumptions—often unconscious beliefs about “the way we do things here” or “the way we are”, leadership, risk, and identity that shape behavior. Among Ethiopian banks, respective deeply embedded assumptions such as these may either foster adaptability and support resilience or inhibit appropriate responses to change. During disruption, organizations anchored in assumptions of control or rigidity may resist transformation even while investing in new technologies and systems or loudly professing progressive values and aspirations (Raz & Fadlon, 2006). In contrast, underlying assumptions that are built on trust, learning, agility, and similar other virtues nurtures institutions to proactively respond to external shocks more strategically.

Edgar Schein (Schein, *Process Consultation Revisited: Building the Helping Relationship*, 1999) claims that meaningful cultural change during disruption must begin by bringing out to the surface and reexamining these deeply embedded basic assumptions. His recommendation for iterative, reflective inquiry is especially relevant in developing markets like Ethiopia, where institutions often face either conflicting expectations or multifaceted changes and legacy

mindsets. The three-level model, when applied holistically, thus offers not just a cultural map but a strategic tool to assess institutional coherence under stress.

In this light, culture becomes neither fixed nor ornamental, it becomes formative. In disrupted ecosystems, the interplay between artifacts, values, and assumptions determines whether an organization bends or breaks. For Ethiopian banks confronting systemic volatility, this cultural depth may be the hidden determinant of future trajectories.

3.4 Identified Gap in the Literature

Although the three-level cultural model was developed four decades ago, Schein's work remained conceptually robust and relevant in dynamic sectors like banking. However, in reviewing existing literatures four key gaps became apparent—conceptual, contextual, methodological, and strategic application gaps.

Much of the existing work focuses on one or two levels out of the three, typically addressing artifacts and/or espoused values, without connecting the dots on how these interact with underlying assumptions in shaping organizational behavior or responses during disruption. Thus, a conceptual gap exists in fully operationalizing the three-level framework in context of disruption. Even if there are studies that do address assumptions, they often struggle with empirical access leading to skewed understanding of cultural alignment (Dimitrov, 2013) (Saiyadain, 2008).

In contemporary contexts like the Ethiopian banks where the institutions are actually going through concurrent systemic and incidental disruptions, existing scholars tends to focus on the implications of the regulatory and macro reforms or socioeconomic issues or the shift towards the increasing adoption of digital strategy and platforms, rarely inspecting how culture mediates these transitions. And such contextual gap remaining unaddressed is clearly displayed in the scarcity of research that examines the cultural substratum of banks navigating regulatory overhaul and policy liberalization, technological advancements and the competitive shifts that came along, and the economic challenges that continue to press on the banks (Abate & Kaur, April 2023) (Berhane, 2019).

Many banks in Ethiopia actually conduct organization culture assessment studies; however, these studies heavily rely on survey-based instruments that are unfitting to capture the interpretive, multi-layered dimensions that Edgar Schein emphasizes to truly decipher, understand, and even influence if one likes to do so. This methodological approach has led to a predominance of surface-level cultural mapping that fails to reveal the congruence or contradictions between visible patterns and hidden beliefs. As Raz and Fadlon (Raz & Fadlon, 2006) caution, without the depth qualitative methodology brings, it rather becomes difficult to discern cultural misalignments or otherwise or cultural inertia—phenomena particularly relevant in conservative, highly regulated sectors like banking.

Despite the extensive evidences presented by the authorities (Kotter & Heskett, 1992) (Cameron & Quinn, 2011) that adaptive cultures correlate strongly with organizational resilience and long-term performance, most banks strategies misses to incorporate culture as key initiative while practically underutilizes it as a vector for transformation. Therefore, strategic application gap persists in spite of the repeated acknowledgement of the banks that culture is important. It should be underlined that culture is rarely treated as a conscious level of disruption management.

Thus, this study positioned itself to make a meaningful contribution that addresses these conceptual, contextual, methodological, strategic application gaps. By applying Edgar Schein's three-levels cultural model within the Ethiopian banking sector using qualitative, document-based thematic analysis, this study aimed to illuminate how culture operates not just descriptively but behaviorally and why that matters during disruption.

4. Results

The results from the 13 sample banks revealed varying degree of manifestation and alignment across the three-levels of corporate culture influencing how the banks in the industry navigate disruption. Through Schein's three-level of cultural lens, the results are summarized and presented below under each research objective to establish practical and theoretical clarity.

4.1 Manifestation of the Three-Levels of Corporate Culture

The three-levels of corporate culture overall are manifested differently across the banks. At a glance, the most visible aspects and the often-overlapping values seem similar. However, the assumptions being the most varied and the difference in congruence and alignment between the three brought the distinction in the manifestation and responses despite having similar conventional and digital gadgets and espoused values.

Banks often manifests artifacts through their physical sites—branches, ATMs, self-service virtual branches, café-style branches, owned or rented furnished HQ buildings and other office space designs. It is also displayed in their digital adoption—the multichannel or omnichannel or Super Apps they are providing to the market; organizational structure, niche market: such as IFB, mortgage, corporate, and HNIs, and last but not least financial performance indicators.

Nonetheless, the level and differing implementation of these visible features, the artifacts, though difficult to decipher the corporate culture a bank has from these, clearly manifested the simmering thinking underneath. For instance: we can categorize the banks into three groups based on the pace and extent of their respective digital adoption. There are leaders that not only have proactive digital strategies, but they are also the swift implementors and rally strategic partners to build platforms including e-commerce or avail services that goes beyond the traditional banking, these banks are the trend setters. The second group are the followers that are steady in their digital adoption and closely follows the leaders, but less aggressive in their growth in this regard. The laggards are basically slower in digital adoption and other changes for that matter.

There are also several other indicators if one takes a careful look at the obvious, such as: focus on physical vs digital channels. Some banks continued to prioritize physical branch expansion, while others either creating balance with the digital platforms or slowing down in opening new branches and most recently a handful of banks are closing branches that are less effective as part of the digitalization process. The organizational structures of the banks also show the digital readiness or the interest to maintain legacies, the respective focus on risk management and corporate governance, and the customer segments and the subsequent emphasis the banks prefer to give for their selected market or the lack of clarity in this regard.

In addition, readiness and ability to adopt to new changes are also among the features observed in this quest. Some banks forge partnerships or aboard new opportunities at every step the financial sector gets opened up despite the challenges that comes along. For instance: early partnerships with fintechs, telecom operators, partnership with development partners and embracing ESG, chartering the newly established securities market, and the list could go on.

Nearly all banks claimed to value innovation, customer focus, resilience, employee development, and integrity in their strategic documents and publicly declared strategic aspirations—the vision, mission, and the core values. However, the operational embodiment of these espoused beliefs and values varies. In many cases, these values were aspirational and not embedded in the decision-making, strategic integration across touchpoints, governance, or talent development trajectories. Similarly, most claim that they are invested on mass market, drive their respective business from there, and promises to provide value to the mass community; however, in reality both the deposit and lending structure displays that the portfolios are held by either mass affluent or corporates. Only a handful drives their business

in alignment with the customer segments they have decided to pursue through their segment-oriented products/services and digital lending platforms.

The last layer, the underlying assumptions, revealed the most divergence. Inferred from the several documents reviewed, artifacts, espoused values, and previous iterative experiences, a handful of banks are adaptive, though the extent differs, operated with the assumptions that disruption is constant and manageable viewing agility and digitalization as norms. Others retained legacy assumptions prioritizing control, hierarchy, or incremental changes. The last but not the least group is those that drives their business with the assumption of following the leaders and having whatever next new thing without clearly understanding the intent and what it contributes for the bank's business. Hence, these varying assumptions has been significantly influencing the speed and depth of resilience, responses, and transformation of each bank.

4.2 Role of Corporate Culture in Shaping Responses to Disruption

All Ethiopian banks encountered the same external shocks—regulatory reforms, rapid technological advancements, and economic challenges. It should be noted that the respective balance sheet size, the number of years they have been around in the market and the experience and infrastructures they have built as a result along similar other factors have had and will continue to have impact on their ability to absorb the shocks. At the same time, age and balance sheet are not the only critical factors since we have seen third generation banks with only three years operation outmaneuvering some of the second-generation banks that have been around for nearly two decades, or few second-generation banks exhibiting the same when it comes to the first-generation banks. As an example, one second-generation bank even transcended and clinched for medium-size bank category among the ranks of only four out of the six first-generation banks that made it.

This is a testament for the role of corporate culture in shaping banks' response to disruption, which was evident through varied patterns of alignment and misalignment across the three levels. The banks responses differed based on the level of cultural coherence between the artifacts, espoused values, and underlying assumptions.

Banks with proactive and integrated responses has been showcasing visible changes such as revamped delivery channels (e.g., virtual branches, café branches, digital lending), introduced new digital platforms (e.g. interbank QR payment, Super Apps, omni-channel platforms, and simmering discussions to introduce AI-supported customer service), restructured risk and treasury units, and adopted agile approaches (e.g. datacenter colocation, partnership with fintech/development partners, rented ATMs and PoS machines). These artifacts were often part of larger transformation programs, backed by resource investment and leadership visibility. Nonetheless, in some banks, digital dashboards or branded campaigns existed without corresponding internal system upgrades, reflecting a surface-level adoption. These institutions pursued compliance with disruption trends rather than transformation.

Among the more adaptive banks, values like agility, customer empowerment, innovation, and partnership were not just declared in strategic documents, but these espoused values were operationalized through fintech alliances, open banking APIs, modular platforms, and decentralization of key services. In less responsive banks, these same values appeared in mission statements but remained ceremonial—unlinked to decision-making or investment logic. Espoused values being the bridge between the two layers, the banks that actually have alignment between their belief and basic assumptions not only effectively translate it to the visible, but also can easily be spotted in the clarity, precision, and focus of their respective execution; while the less congruent ones are visible for lack there off despite having all the gadgets required within the spectrum.

Lastly, it should be noted that Ethiopia having been a closed market until very recently, such significantly notable regulatory shifts that also fostered disruption from all the remaining

aspects, is new to all banks. Despite the asset size, the generation gap and having more time to build infrastructures and routines, what is really setting the banks apart is the way they view disruption in the first place; since the core differentiator in all of this is the dominant underlying assumptions about disruption.

The relatively adaptive banks viewed change as an enabler and started to recalibrate their structures, position themselves for growth, and venture into new partnerships and business models. At least they are not afraid of to roll the dice. Now, in contrast, banks which are less adaptive operate under the assumptions of disruption as a threat. As a result, they end up with fragmented responses, stuck in various committees that does not actually get things done, in general internal delays, and excessive focus on cost reduction rather than strategic alignment.

4.3 Most Influential Cultural Element in Navigating Disruption

Instead of one of the cultural elements surfacing as a single most influential aspect to effectively navigate the disruption, the alignment across the levels turned out to be the effective driver. Especially when adaptable underlying assumptions led the way in creating coherence with both artifacts and espoused values.

Visible changes in artifacts, such as rebranding, implementation of modern tools, introduction of new products, and digital interfaces, might appear that the bank is progressing and going in the right direction. Nonetheless, the change might only be superficial and such changes alone are not enough. What made real difference were artifacts intentionally designed to fulfill the bank's strategic intent. For instance: products tailored to specifically address a certain location demand, data-driven customer insights, aggregated services in a single platform, and credit scoring systems, which goes beyond mere symbolism. They actively influence the routine of customers and the experience they get out of the encounter, which ultimately translates innovation into measurable impact.

Banks that embedded innovation and resilience into their identity, as decreed in their espoused values, demonstrated a greater capacity to adapt. These espoused values, often with a sense of urgency and purpose, nurtured corporate-wide permission challenge legacy thinking, pursue new business models, reallocate resources, and form strategic partnerships.

Despite the optimum alignment between the elements, it was at the underlying assumptions—the deepest level that true cultural transformation realized. Take note that the true alignment is only realized and sustains when both the artifacts and espoused values emanate from this core level. Banks with adaptive assumptions such as “bringing the right balance for the changing demography”, “technology is a strategic driver”, or “regulator change is growth enabler” fostered sustainable alignment. Such as: some are introducing branch models that are tailored to shifting demography; others are building on Data Lakehouse based on their belief that data is the primary battleground for competitiveness; and the others launched structural changes and advancement into new businesses to cope up with the regulatory changes.

These deep-seated assumptions ensured consistency and alignment between what the bank claimed, what it portrayed, and what it actually did. In such institutions, culture functioned much more than static set of branding exercise or set of ideals, but a dynamic system that is alive, evolving, and responsive to disruption.

4.4 Influence of the Three Cultural Levels on Banks' Trajectory During Disruption

Although most banks do not assume active role of consciously designing and embedding corporate culture to effectively drive their operations other than conducting annual or occasional organizational culture assessment, the influence of the three levels of corporate culture, i.e., artifacts, espoused values, and underlying assumptions, actually played a defining role in shaping how banks navigated disruption. Each level had a different contribution, but

aligned, they formed a cultural foundation that shaped the banks' strategic direction, capacity to respond, and institutional resilience.

Apparently, banks that displayed comprehensive and coherent physical and digital artifacts were often better positioned in the market. These visible to the eye, senses, and macro-culture elements, such as: contemporary brands, modern branches, upgraded digital platforms, tailored relationship management, and customer service and complaint management tools afforded enhanced operational efficiency and customer experience. Nonetheless, the significance and sustainability of their impact was considerable when backed with genuine internal readiness that effortlessly originated from underlying assumptions. Artifacts became enablers of proactive responsiveness and strategic accomplishments far beyond mere symbols where deep-seated culture supported the use and purpose of tools that are being implemented at this level. Espoused values, beneath the surface, such as: transparency, adaptability, customer-centricity, learning organization, and social responsibility stated in the core values or being the innovator in the market or the means to assume success or an alternative that brings relevance to one's life as claimed in the taglines, served as stabilizers that kept banks grounded during times of such uncertainty and disruption. This only realized in institutions where these stated values and taglines were truly internalized and in congruence with the deep-seated assumptions. In these banks, VMVs, guiding principles, and policies went far and beyond mere statements, they actively shaped strategy execution, created a shared language and mindset, and anchored teams to work towards coordinated responses even in the face of adversity.

Ultimately, it was the underlying assumptions that determined the trajectory and resilience of the banks. Without the proper alignment, artifacts remain superficial and espoused values disconnected from what is simmering at the deepest level. Banks with deeply embedded assumptions of systemic thinking, proactive learning, openness to change, and capability-based outlook demonstrated greater resilience and agility. Whereas banks operating from bureaucratic control, excessive risk aversion and cost reduction, or rigid hierarchy tended to stagnate unable to break free from outdated practices in spite of the returns they are recording right now.

In general, it should be noted that it was not any single cultural element that defined any of the banks' trajectory during such season, rather the dynamic alignment and interplay between all the three levels. When the cultural elements were aligned and harmonized in progressive and adaptive assumptions, Banks were not only able to weather through the ongoing disruption but able to grow through it, particularly in laying down roots for sustainable long-term growth potentially far greater than the short-term returns they are recording now.

5. Discussion

This study set out to examine how the corporate culture, particularly using Edgar Schein's three levels of culture—artifacts, espoused beliefs and values, and underlying assumptions, shapes Ethiopian banks' trajectory and ability to navigate through the disruption that is coming on their way from regulatory changes, technological advancements, and economic challenges. Following similar thematical pattern as the results, the discussion interprets the findings that are drawn from the rich qualitative insights in alignment with the study's objectives and contextualizes them in the existing literature.

Again, similar pattern to the findings each objective in this analysis was examined through the cultural lenses; and overall outcome of the analysis suggests that corporate culture is not mere depiction of organizations features or character, rather a dynamic and decisive factor that has a notable impact in determining the response of banks to disruption and shapes their respective trajectory accordingly.

5.1 Manifestation of the Three-Levels of Corporate Culture

The study revealed a visible similarity in artifacts and espoused values across most banks, with equally striking divergence in underlying assumptions. While nearly all banks move with similar rhythm, from providing similar products to revamping digital platforms, and corporate brands and also articulated values such as: social responsibility, innovation, adaptability, and customer-centricity, only few were able to attain genuine alignment with the foundational assumptions or consciously reshaping to bridge such gaps.

This circumstance exactly fits the context in which Schein suggested that one should be cautious. Since artifacts, though easily visible are difficult to decipher, and they can be superficial and misleading in case they are not rooted in deeper cultural elements (Schien, 2010). And such pattern reflects what Raz and Fadlon describes as “performative culture” (Raz & Fadlon, 2006), where superficial changes obscure deep-seated resistance to adaptability and transformation. For instance, banks may exhibit an image of innovation and progressiveness while operating from a deeply-rooted conventional thinking. Introducing a new branch model, digital platform, claiming to embrace ESG, or contemporary tagline that advocates digital adoption, yet retaining legacy operational models and decision hierarchies while skipping the rigorous work required to bring the mindset shift could not be a better example.

Hence, the different manifestation of culture using the three level lenses across the banks is not only the result of strategic orientation and operational direction, but also the clear disparity in authenticity and institutional coherence. This variation from bank to bank is critical, as it has a direct, but often unnoticed, influence in sharing their respective trajectories in a meaningful and sustainable way.

5.2 Role of Corporate Culture in Shaping Responses to Disruption

Culture emerged as a key factor in determining how banks responded to disruption. Banks that were culturally aligned across all three levels, where the visible, values, and deep-seated norms were consistent, responded more effectively and continue to rise to the occasion of such uncertain times. On the contrary, those banks that lacked cultural alignment, even with strong and contemporary artifacts, displayed fragmented, reactive, and compliance-oriented responses.

The findings of this study match with Kotter Heskett’s statement (Kotter & Heskett, 1992) that adaptive cultures outperform non-adaptive ones, particularly in environment characterized to be turbulent. More specifically, the findings highlight the risk of dissonance: when what is said (values) and what is done (artifacts) diverges from what is believed (assumptions), it results confusion in strategic direction, institutional misalignment, and sluggish execution. Some banks launched fintech partnerships or fancy digital platforms or revamp their corporate brands; however, they still retained legacy operating models, risk-averse governance structures, thus ended up limiting their ability for effective and proactive responses as well as confusion in their way to play. As a result, they have become the practical examples of the abovementioned discord.

In contrast, banks that viewed disruption as an opportunity rather than as a threat with deeply-rooted norms of authenticity, opportunity seeking, genuine drive for learning, strategic flexibility, and true strategic partnership are sawing and will sustainably reap a different outcome than their prior counterparts. Since these underlying assumptions served and will continue to serve as invisible yet powerful engine for adaptability, responsiveness, and decision-making. This finding is the reflection of Schein’s argument (Schein, Process Consultation Revisited: Building the Helping Relationship, 1999) that culture, when surfaced and reflected upon, can become a strategic enabler rather than a barrier to change.

5.3 Most Influential Cultural Element in Navigating Disruption

The findings of this study reinforce Schein's core thesis that underlying assumptions, more than artifacts and espoused values, drive behavior, responsiveness ability, and in general institutional outcomes. While artifacts are visible to the eye and if aligned well, signals intent, and espoused values articulates aspirations, it is the deeply-seated assumptions that determine what is normal, what should be avoided, or how quickly the bank shift to proactively or reactively respond to circumstances.

Banks, that are actually learning to the core and genuinely invested in continuous learning and assumed disruption is inevitable, rather the way the respond could only be managed, are now benefiting and will continue to do so with the ability they have created to move early, consistently, and remain resilient. On the other hand, others that clung to their legacy assumptions, past successes, and regarded disruption as something to be avoided, despite the posh look and feel or public expression of transformation, are defaulting to incremental adjustments or passive compliance.

This underscores the importance of cultural congruence: alignment across the visible, the values, and the assumptions, in shaping trajectories to bring a desired outcome of coherent institutional identity and strategic direction. In cases where such alignments are missing, Banks experienced and will continue to do so what Cameron & Quinn refer as "cultural stall" (Cameron & Quinn, 2011), where progress is initiated but not sustained due to unaddressed internal alignment issues.

5.4 Influence of the Three Cultural Levels on Banks' Trajectory During Disruption

The combined findings from all three objectives displayed that different cultural configurations result divergent institutional trajectories. Banks that possess aligned and adaptive cultures have demonstrated actual agility, fortified digital foresight, and proactive changes. These banks are not only keeping pace with change, but actively shaping their way to play and overall strategic direction despite the ongoing disruption coming from all three critical fronts. However, banks with outdated or misaligned assumptions are struggling to evolve. These banks response to the disruption is as fragmented as their respective culture and they tend to respond cautiously more often focusing on regulatory compliance rather than transformation.

This clear difference implies that the future trajectories of banks in Ethiopia will depend far beyond the asset sizes, the strength of the capital, or even technology, and more on cultural alignment and depth since the stated tools and platforms could only be put to good use with good cultural clarity and alignment.

In a context marked by multilayered disruption like Ethiopia, banks cannot afford to use culture as a symbolic act that can be addressed with occasional assessment studies, rather it is a necessity that definitely brings competitive advantage. Banks that understands this and deliberately shape up and align their culture can use to drive transformation and remain resilient; whereas, those that ignore it will the suffer the consequence of strategic drift.

6. Conclusion and Practical Implications

6.1 Conclusion

This study intended to investigate the role of corporate culture, in light of Edgar Schein's three levels framework: artifacts, espoused beliefs and values, and underlying assumptions, in shaping the trajectory of Ethiopian Banks' that are facing disruption from three critical aspects—regulatory, technology, and national economy. The results and discussions, a thematic analysis based on qualitative data from 13 sample banks, emphasized that culture is neither luxury nor auxiliary in a bank's journey to sustainable growth, adaptability, and resilience. It

is, rather, a central force that informs how the banks perceive, interpret, and respond in the face of uncertainties.

While most banks demonstrated the possession of similar products, digital platforms, branch aesthetics, value statements, and policy documents, which shows the presence of comparable artifacts and espoused values, the difference in their respective deeply-seated assumptions has been the critical differentiator in the institutional responses and outcomes. The level of alignment or the lack thereof between the visible, the values, and the deeper norms explains much of the variation noted in their ability to respond, move early, proactively engage regulator, and remain resilient. In cases of banks where underlying assumptions are genuinely rooted in continuous learning, agility, adaptability, and proactiveness, the banks' artifacts and espoused values follow suit, resulting in proactive and coherent transformation. Whereas, where the underlying assumptions remained outdated, fragmented or performative, transformation remains surface-level at best since the posh artifacts and values are superficial without real connection to the root.

Ultimately, this study underscores the need for Ethiopian banks to treat culture not as a fixed backdrop or compliance exercise, but as a living system to be aligned, cultivated, and strategically led since the dynamic interplay between the three levels of culture will not only determine the now operation, but also the long-term strategic direction.

6.2 Practical Implications

Attaining its ultimate goal of providing preliminary findings that would enable a better understanding of the market dynamics in light of corporate culture, the study yields multiple practical implications for practitioners and future researchers.

Treat culture as integral part of strategy: the relationship between culture and strategy goes far beyond the famous “culture eats strategy for breakfast” saying (Drucker, 2012). A great strategy with the wrong culture is doomed, a strong culture without strategy leads to stagnation; but when culture and strategy align, business thrives. Therefore, culture is not an HR initiative or branding concern, rather ensuring alignment across artifacts, espoused values, and underlying assumptions should be a deliberate and integral part of strategic planning.

Avoid the Trap of Performative Culture and Embed it in every Change Program: rebranding and digital migration efforts that are not backed by genuine cultural conviction tend to stall. Banks must resist the urge to mimic innovation without embedding it into routines, talent systems, and governance. Particularly during disruption, the assumptions embedded in leadership styles, risk appetite, or innovation posture become either accelerators or bottlenecks. Leaders must foster internal dialogue to question and evolve these beliefs.

Any transformation efforts, be it digital, regulatory, or structure, must include a cultural component. Cultural artifacts should be supported by realigned values and deeply-rooted internal narratives.

Embed Culture in KPIs: use storytelling, dialogue forums, and leadership modeling to reinforce shared meaning, especially during such time of so many uncertainties. And subsequently support the inculcation process by introducing monitoring and recognition systems, such as measuring cultural indicators like cross-functional collaboration, responsiveness to change, openness to feedback, learning, inclusivity, and innovation.

Future Research Directions: future researchers should explore relationship between cultural alignment and performance in-depth, especially by focusing on specific cases of high and low performing banks sustaining in disruptive contexts. Plus, comparative studies across sectors or boundary lines could be a good area of research to cover new grounds.

Bibliography

- Abate, M. T., & Kaur, R. (April 2023). Banking Sector in Ethiopia: Origin and Present State. *EPH - International Journal of Business & Management*, Volume 09 Issue 02.
- Accion. (2025, February 18). Ethiopia's Digital Banking Innovation: Partnering for Financial Inclusion . Retrieved from Accion Website: <https://www.accion.org/news/>
- Barney, J. B. (Jul. 1986). Organization Culture: Can it be a Source of Sustained Competitive Advantage? *The Academy of Management Review*, Vol.11, No. 3, 656-664.
- Berhane, S. (2019, Nov. - Dec. 15 - 16). A New Wave of Change in the Banking Industry. *Ethiopian Business Review*.
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using Thematic Analysis in Psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77 - 101.
- Cameron, K. S., & Quinn, R. E. (2011). *Diagnosing and Changing Organizational Culture: Based on the Competing Values Framework* (3rd ed). San Francisco, CA: John Wiley & Sons.
- Christensen, C. M., Raynor, M., & McDonald, R. (2015). What is Disruptive Innovation? *Harvard Business Review*, 93(12), 44-53.
- Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Qualitative Inquiry and Research Design: Choosing Among Five Approaches* (3rd ed). Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications.
- Crotty, M. (1988). *The Foundations of Social Research: Meaning and Perspective in the Research Process*. London: SAGE Publications.
- Deal, T. E., & Kennedy, A. A. (2000). *Corporate Cultures: The Rites and Rituals of Corporate Life* (Rev. ed). Basic Books.
- Denzin, N. K., & Lincoln, Y. S. (2018). *The SAGE Handbook of Qualitative Research* (5th ed). SAGE.
- Dimitrov, K. (2013). Edgar Schein's Model of Organizational Culture Levels as a Hologram. *Economic Studies* (Ikonicheski Izsledvania), ISSN 0205-3292, Bulgarian Academy of, 3 - 36.
- Drucker, P. F. (2012). *Management Challenges for the 21st Century*, eBook. London: Routledge.
- FAO. (2023). *Ukraine: Humanitarian Response Update*. Kyiv: Food and Agriculture Organization of United Nations.
- FDRE House of Representatives. (2025, March 12). Banking Business Proclamation No. 1360/2025. *Federal Negarit Gazette*. Addis Ababa, Addis Ababa, Addis Ababa: Berhan and Selam Publishing Company.
- Godart, F., & Pistilli, L. (2024). The Multifaceted Conception of Disruption: A typology. *Journal of Business Research*, Volume 170, 114311.
- Goldkuhl, G. (2012). Pragmatism vs Interpretivism in Qualitative Information Systems Research. *European Journal of Information Systems*, 21(2), 135 - 146.
- Hofstede, G. (2010). *Cultures and Organizations: Software of the Mind* (3rd ed). McGraw-Hill.
- Iger, R. (2019). *The Ride of a Lifetime*. New York: Random House Publishing Group.
- Kotter, J. P., & Heskett, J. L. (1992). *Corporate Culture and Performance*. New York: Free Press.
- Lelisa, T. B., & Tadesse, M. W. (July 2024). The Impact of Minimum Regulatory Capital Requirements on the Performance of Banks: The Case of Ethiopian Private Commercial Banks. *International Journal of Economics, Commercial and Management*, Vol. 12, Issue 7, 39 - 58.
- Mastercard Foundation . (2025, March 28). The Mastercard Foundation And Kifiya Financial Technology Honour Over 100 Graduates Of SAFE Program, Specializing In AI And Data Science. Retrieved from Mastercard Foundation Website: <https://mastercardfdn.org/en/news/the-mastercard-foundation-and-kifiya-financial-technology-honour-over-100-graduates-of-safe-program-specializing-in-ai-and-data-science/>
- Merriam-Webster. (2025, February 24). Merriam-Webster. Retrieved from <https://www.merriam-webster.com:https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/disruption>
- Ministry of Finance. (2023). *Macro-Fiscal: Performance in Ethiopia and Recent Fiscal Policy Developments*. Addis Ababa: MoF.
- Ministry of Planning and Development. (2025, April). MoPD Report. Retrieved from MoPD Website: <https://www.mopd.gov.et/en/MoPDcoreDivision/data/>
- Morgan, D. L. (2007). Paradigms Lost and Pragmatism Regained: Methodological Implications of Combining Qualitative and Quantitative Methods. *Journal of Mixed Method Research*, 1(1), 48 - 76.
- National Bank of Ethiopia . (2024, July 29). Foreign Exchange Directive No. FXD/01/2024. Addis Ababa, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia: <https://www.nbe.gov.et>.
- National Bank of Ethiopia. (2021). *National Digital Payment Strategy 2021 - 2024*. Retrieved from National Bank of Ethiopia Website : <https://nbe.gov.et/files/national-digital-payment-strategy-2/>
- National Bank of Ethiopia. (2023). *Annual Report of 2021/22*. Addis Ababa: NBE.
- National Bank of Ethiopia. (2023, December). *NBE's Strategic Plan for 2023-26*. Retrieved from National Bank of Ethiopia Website : <https://nbe.gov.et/plan/>
- National Bank of Ethiopia. (2025, February 24). Retrieved February 24, 2025, from <https://nbe.gov.et:https://nbe.gov.et/financial-institutions/banks/>

- National Bank of Ethiopia. (2025). Quarterly Bulletin: Fourth Quarter 2023/24. Addis Ababa: NBE.
- NBE. (2024). Quarter Bulletin: Fourth Quarter of 2022/23. Addis Ababa: NBE.
- NBE. (November 2024). Financial Stability Report. Addis Ababa: National Bank of Ethiopia, www.nbe.gov.et.
- Patton, M. Q. (2015). *Qualitative Research & Evaluation Methods* (4th ed). Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE.
- PYMNTS. (2022, August 31). Mobile Money Earns Its Stripes in Ethiopia's Telecom Liberalization . Retrieved from PYMNTS Website: <https://www.pymnts.com/news/mobile-payments/2022/mobile-money-earns-its-stripes-in-ethiopias-telecom-liberalization/>
- Raz, A. E., & Fadlon, J. (2006). Managerial Culture, Workplace Culture and Situated Curricula in Organizational Learning. *Organization Studies*, 27(2), 165 - 182.
- Robbins, S. P., & Judge, T. A. (2013). *Organizational Behavior* (15th ed.). Boston, MA: Pearson.
- Robinson, O. (2014). Sampling in Interview-Based Qualitative Research: A Theoretical and Practical Guide. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 11 (1), 25 - 41.
- Robson, C. (2011). *Real World Research* (3rd ed). Wiley.
- Saiyadain, M. S. (2008). *Human Resources Management* (4th ed.). New Delhi: Tata McGraw Hill Publishing.
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P., & Thornhill, A. (2016). *Research Methods for Business Students* (7th ed.). Italy : Pearson Education Limited.
- Schein, E. H. (1999). *Process Consultation Revisited: Building the Helping Relationship*. San Francisco, CA: Addison-Wesely .
- Schein, E. H. (2004). *Organizational Culture and Leadership* (3rd ed). San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Schien, E. H. (2010). *Organizational Culture and Leadership* (4th ed.). San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- The Swing of Paid up Capital over the Years. (2021, April 19). *Captial* .
- Thomas, D. R. (2006). A General Inductive Approach for Analyzing Qualitative Evaluation Data. *American Journal of Evaluation*, 27(2), 237 - 246.
- UNCTAD. (2022). *Global Trade: The Ripple of Effect of the Ukraine Crisis*. Geneva: UNCTAD Annual Report.
- UNDP. (2024, January 30). *Digital Lending Platforms: Unlocking Access to Finance in Ethiopia*. Retrieved from UNDP Webstie: <https://www.undp.org/ethiopia/blog/digital-lending-platforms>
- World Bank . (2023). *Ethiopia Economic Update: Navigating Inflation and FX Pressures* . Washington, DC: The World Bank Group.
- World Bank. (2025). *The Deepening Red Sea Shipping Crisis: Impact and Outlook*. Washington, DC: The World Bank Group.